

Synthesis of diketopiperazines containing prolinyl unit – cyclo(L-prolinyl-L-leucine), cyclo(L-prolinyl-L-isoleucine) and cyclo(L-tryptophyl-L-proline)

S. Jhaumeer-Laulloo*, A. Khodabocus, A. Jugoo, D. Jheengut and S. Sobha

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, University of Mauritius, Réduit, Mauritius

E-mail : sabina@uom.ac.mu Fax : 230-4656928

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Diketopiperazines cyclo(L-prolinyl-L-isoleucine) **4a**, cyclo(L-prolinyl-L-leucine) **4b** and cyclo(L-tryptophyl-L-proline) **6** were prepared from their respective suitably protected amino acid derivatives by standard peptide chemistry. Cyclo(L-(4-hydroxyprolinyl)-L-phenylalanine) **3**, **4a** and cyclo(L-prolinyl-L-tyrosine) **5** were tested for their antibacterial activity.

2,5-Diketopiperazines, formed by cyclization of dipeptides, are interesting compounds because of their important biological properties¹⁻³. Diketopiperazines have been isolated from plants mainly marine sponges⁴, microorganisms as well as from higher animals⁵. 2,5-Diketopiperazines are also obtained as by-products during the process of acidic or enzymatic digestion of proteinous stuff using mammalian or bacterial protease⁶.

Suzuki *et al.*⁷ synthesized a number of analogs cyclo(Tyr-Arg) **1** and have studied their analgesic properties in mice. Many of these diketopiperazines contain proline and hydroxyproline and most of them exhibit important biological properties⁷. Recently, the diketopiperazines, cyclo[L-(4-hydroxyproline)-L-leucine], cyclo[L-(4-hydroxyprolinyl)-D-leu-

cine], **2a** and **2b** and cyclo[L-(4-hydroxyprolinyl)-L-phenylalanine]⁸ **3** have been isolated from *Palythoa* sp., a marine bacterium³, and are shown to stimulate plant growth. Herein we report the preparation of diketopiperazines **4a**, **4b** and **6** and the biological activity of **3**, **4a** and **5**⁹ (Chart 1).

Results and discussion

The target molecules were individually synthesized using the plan depicted in Schemes 1 and 2 beginning with the appropriate amino acids. The amino group of the L-proline was first protected using benzylchloroformate in alkaline medium. L-Isoleucine and L-leucine were converted into their corresponding ester hydrochloride by refluxing the amino acid in absolute ethanol in the presence of thionyl chloride. The ester hydrochlorides obtained were washed with K₂CO₃ to obtain the pure ethyl esters **7a** and **7b**. The use of concentrated sulfuric acid as catalyst provided the desired esters in lower yields (45%).

Coupling of protected amino acids were accomplished with dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC) in dry DCM at room temperature to give dipeptides **8a** and **8b**.

Prior to cyclization of the dipeptides, the prolinylamino group was deprotected using transfer hydrogenation by refluxing the dipeptide in MeOH in the presence of Pd-C and cyclohexene afforded the *N*-deprotected products **9a** and **9b**. The peaks corresponding to the benzylic protons of the *Z*-group at δ 7.3 and 5.1 were absent in the ¹H NMR spectra of **9a** and **9b**, confirming that the *Z*-group had been successfully removed.

The final step of the reaction involved the cyclization of the dipeptides **9a** and **9b**. This was first attempted using DMAP in refluxing toluene but the reaction was unsuccessful. Use of higher boiling solvents such as xylene did

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) $PhCH_2OCOCI$, NaOH (aq.), 0° , RT, 80%, (ii) DCC, RT, (iii) cyclohexene, Pd-C, MeOH, reflux, (iv) K_2CO_3 , $(CH_2OH)_2$, reflux.

not improve the situation. Refluxing the dipeptide in xylene in the presence of NaH as base also did not yield the targeted molecules since after work up, the 1H NMR spectrum showed the presence of the ester peaks (δ 4.1 and 1.1). In the light of these results, it was decided to conduct the cyclization via saponification of the ester. The latter reaction was successfully accomplished using lithium hydroxide since the 1H NMR spectrum of the reaction mixture showed the absence of the ethyl ester peaks. However, due presumably to the high solubility of the resulting ammonium salt in water, the work-up using dilute mineral acid proved to be very difficult.

Refluxing the dipeptide **9a** at 180° in ethylene glycol

Scheme 2. Reagents: (i) Boc_2O , Et_3N , RT, 83%, (ii) DCC, HBOT, RT, 74%, (iii) TFA, RT, 85%, (iv) K_2CO_3 , $(CH_2OH)_2$, reflux, 30%.

using a catalytic amount of potassium carbonate finally yielded the cyclo(L-prolinyl-L-isoleucine) **4a**. The same procedure yielded also the isomer **4b** (Scheme 1).

For the diketopiperazine **6** the α -NH of tryptophan was protected as the BOC group using BOC anhydride in the presence of triethylamine (TEA). Coupling of the BOC-protected tryptophan **10** with proline ethyl ester **11** using DCC and 1,1-hydroxybenzotriazole in the presence of TEA yielded the dipeptide **12**.

Treatment of the dipeptide **12** with TFA gave the deprotected dipeptide **13**. The absence of the intense singlet at δ 1.1 ppm confirmed that BOC was effectively removed. The dipeptide **13** underwent cyclization by refluxing in ethylene glycol using catalytic amount of K_2CO_3 to give the diketopiperazine **6** (Scheme 2).

Antibacterial screening of all the compounds were carried out, using the Gram-positive bacterium *Staphylococcus aureus*, and the Gram-negative bacteria, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Salmonella typhimerium*. Blank tests showed that DMSO and water used in the preparation of the test solutions did not affect the growth of the microorganisms. Antibacterial activity of the different diketopiperazines **3**, **4a** and **5** was evaluated at concentration of $1600 \mu g ml^{-1}$. Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTBA) was used as control. The diketopiperazine **3** containing a hydroxyl group was found active against *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus*. The other dipeptides were found inactive. Hence, antibacterial activity of **3** was further studied using different concentrations ($1600, 800, 400, 200$ and $100 \mu g ml^{-1}$) in DMSO and the zone of inhibition was measured. At a concentration of $1600 \mu g ml^{-1}$, **3** inhibited the growth of *P. aeruginosa* with an inhibition zone of 15.5 mm while it inhibited the growth of *S. aureus* with an inhibition zone of 10.5 mm. CTBA inhibited the growth of both the bacteria with inhibition zone of 20 mm. **3** inhibited the activity of *S. aureus* at a minimum concentration of $400 \mu g ml^{-1}$ (7.0 mm) while it was still active *P. aeruginosa* at a concentration of $100 \mu g ml^{-1}$ (9.5 mm).

Experimental

1H and ^{13}C spectra ($CDCl_3$) were recorded on a Bruker Spectrospin instrument at 250 MHz with TMS as internal standard and IR spectra on a Mattson Genesis II series FTIR spectrophotometer. Chromatography refers to the 'flash column' technique over silica gel (70–230 mesh). TLC was carried out on plates pre-coated with silica and visualized by exposure to iodine vapour. C, H, N were analyzed on a LECO CHNS-932 analyzer. All chemicals were of A.R. grade except methanol, which was of GPR grade. Methanol

was distilled and kept over molecular sieves.

N-(*Benzyloxycarbonyl*)-*L*-proline : To a ice-cold (0°) solution of *L*-proline (1.5 g, 13.05 mmol) dissolved in 4 *M* NaOH (6.3 ml, 27.41 mmol, 2.1 eq), benzyl chloroformate (2.26 g, 15.66 mmol, 1.3 eq) was added dropwise over a period of 20 min with stirring while maintaining the temperature at 0°. The mixture was further stirred for 2 h with gradual warming to room temperature while monitoring the progress of the reaction by TLC (methanol/glacial acetic acid, 19 : 1, *R_f* 0.6). The reaction mixture was then diluted with water (10 ml) and extracted with diethyl ether (2 × 10 ml). The resulting aqueous phase was acidified with HCl (1 : 1). The liberated oil was extracted with ether (5 × 10 ml) and dried over anhyd. sodium sulfate. Evaporation of the solvent gave the product as a very pale yellow viscous liquid (2.6 g, 80%); ν_{\max} 3400 (NH), 1693 and 1702 cm^{-1} (CO); δ_{H} 7.0–7.3 (5H, m, aromatic CH), 5.1 (2H, m, benzylic CH₂), 4.5 (1H, m, CH), 3.5 (2H, m, CH₂), 1.9–2.18 (4H, m, 2 × CH₂).

Isoleucine ethyl ester 7a. Method A : To a stirred, ice-cold suspension of isoleucine (1.5 g, 11.45 mmol) in absolute ethanol (50 ml), thionyl chloride (2.1 g, 17.17 mmol, 1.275 ml, 1.5 eq) was added dropwise and the mixture was refluxed for 3.5 h. The resulting pale yellow solution when evaporated *in vacuo* gave an oily liquid. It was mixed with DCM (10 ml) and the isoleucine ester was neutralized by adding aq. NaHCO₃ (4 × 5 ml). The organic layer was dried over anhyd. sodium sulfate. Evaporation of the solvent gave viscous yellow-brown liquid (1.183 g, 65%); ν_{\max} 1729 cm^{-1} (CO); δ_{H} 4.2 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz, CH₂ of ester), 3.4 (1H, d, *J* 5 Hz), 1.8 (1H, m), 1.4 (1H, m), 1.3 (1H, m), 1.2 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz), 0.9 (6H, m).

Method B : To a stirred, ice-cold suspension of isoleucine (1.5 g, 11.45 mmol) in absolute ethanol (50 ml), a few drops of conc. sulfuric acid (0.5 ml) were added and the mixture was refluxed for 4 h. The pale yellow solution obtained was allowed to stand at room temperature overnight and the ethanol was evaporated *in vacuo*. The resulting viscous liquid was mixed with DCM (10 ml) and the acidic isoleucine ester was neutralized by adding aq. NaHCO₃ (4 × 5 ml). The organic layer was dried over anhyd. sodium sulfate. Evaporation of the solvent on a rotary evaporator left a viscous yellow-brown liquid (0.819 g, 45% yield). Method A was repeated for the preparation of leucine ethyl ester **7b** : δ_{H} 4.2 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz), 3.9 (1H, t, *J* 6 Hz), 1.6 (1H, m), 1.5 (2H, m), 1.2 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz), 0.9 (6H, m); δ_{C} 171.3, 63.9, 51.9, 39.2, 24.4, 21.4, 13.6 ppm.

N-(*Benzyloxycarbonyl*)-*L*-proline-*L*-isoleucine ethyl ester **8a** : To a solution of the partially protected proline

derivative (2.6 g, 10.44 mmol) in DCM (10 ml), isoleucine ester (1.66 g, 10.44 mmol) was added. After 4 h, the *N,N*-dicyclohexylurea derivative formed was washed with DCM and the product, a pale yellow viscous liquid, was purified by column chromatography (EtOAc and hexane, 2 : 1; 15 ml). Evaporation of the solvent yielded the desired dipeptide as a viscous oil, which solidified on cooling (3.39 g, 85%); ν_{\max} 3372 (NH), 1732 (CO), 1688 cm^{-1} (CO); δ_{H} 7.3 (5H, m), 6.4 (1H, bs, NH), 5.1 (2H, s), 4.5 (1H, bs), 4.4 (1H, bs), 4.2 (2H, bs), 3.5 (2H, m), 1.7–1.9 (5H, m), 1.1–1.3 (5H, m), 0.9 (6H, m); δ_{C} 180, 171.6, 128.5, 128.0, 127.8, 67.3, 61.1, 58.9, 56, 49, 37.8, 35, 29, 25.1, 15.4, 14.2, 11.6 ppm. *N*-(*Benzyloxycarbonyl*)-*L*-proline-*L*-leucine ethyl ester **8b** : Yield 60%; δ_{H} 7.1–7.3 (5H, m), 5.1 (2H, s), 4.3 (2H, m), 4.1 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz), 3.5 (2H, m), 2.1–2.3 (4H, m), 1.5–1.6 (3H, t), 1.15 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz), 0.9 (6H, m).

Prolinyl-L-isoleucine ethyl ester 9a : To a solution of the protected peptide **8a** (3.39 g, 8.692 mmol) in methanol (20 ml) were added cyclohexene (10 ml) and catalytic amount of activated palladium on carbon. The mixture was refluxed for 5 h, and then purified by column chromatography by eluting first with EtOAc then with methanol. Evaporation of the methanol fraction gave a viscous yellow substance (1.99 g, 90%); ν_{\max} 3314–3462 (NH) 1665 (CO amide), 1738 cm^{-1} (CO ester); δ_{H} 5.3 (1H, NH), 4.5 (1H, dd, *J* 7 Hz, 5 Hz), 4.3 (2H, q, *J* 6 Hz), 3.8 (1H, dd, *J* 7.3 Hz, *J* 5 Hz), 2.9–3.0 (2H, m), 1.9–2.0 (3H, m), 1.7 (2H, m), 1.4 (1H, m), 1.2 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz), 1.1 (1H, m), 0.9 (6H, m). *Prolinyl-L-leucine ethyl ester 9b* : Yield 50%; δ_{H} 4.5 (1H, m), 4.1 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz), 3.9 (1H, m), 3.0 (2H, t, *J* 7 Hz), 2.2 (1H, m), 1.8–2.0 (2H, m), 1.5–1.6 (2H, m), 1.2 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz), 1.1 (2H, m), 0.9 (6H, d, *J* 7.25 Hz).

Cyclo(L-prolinyl-L-isoleucine) 4a : To a solution of *N*-deprotected peptide **9a** (1.99 g, 7.80 mmol) in ethylene glycol (15 ml), potassium carbonate (1 g, 1 eq) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 5 h, then diluted with water (15 ml) and extracted with ethyl acetate (5 × 10 ml). The organic layer was dried (Na₂SO₄) and evaporated to give a reddish-brown paste. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (EtOAc) to a brownish paste (0.716 g, 46%) in 30% overall yield starting from *L*-proline : δ_{H} 4.0 (1H, m), 3.6 (1H, m), 3.5 (1H, m), 3.4 (1H, m), 2.3 (1H, m), 1.8 (4H, m), 1.4 (1H, m), 1.1 (1H, m), 0.9 (6H, m); δ_{C} 174.6, 169, 63, 60, 58.9, 46, 26, 16, 15, 11 ppm; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{20}$ 4.426 (CHCl₃). *Cyclo(L-prolinyl-L-leucine) 4b* : Yield 52%; δ_{H} 4.0 (1H, t, *J* 7.3 Hz), 3.8 (1H, t, *J* 7.3 Hz), 3.5 (2H, t), 1.9–2.3 (5H, m), 1.5 (1H, m), 1.1 (1H, m), 0.9 (6H, m).

N-t-Butyloxycarbonyltryptophan 10 : To a stirred suspension of tryptophan (0.5 g, 2.5 mmol) in methanol, TEA (5 ml) and Boc₂O (0.53 g) were added. The reaction mixture was stirred for 24 h at room temperature. The reaction was monitored by TLC (EtOAc : Hex, 1 : 1, R_f : 0.86). Methanol was then evaporated and a yellow paste was obtained. A minimum amount of water was added to the reaction mixture and extracted with diethyl ether (2 × 25 ml), washed with brine (20 ml), dried (Na₂SO₄) and on evaporation a yellow paste was obtained (0.60 g, 80%); ν_{\max} 3300 (NH), 1710, 1690 cm⁻¹ (CO); δ_H 8.1 (1H, s), 7.5 (4H, m), 4.4 (1H, m), 4.0 (2H, q), 3.2 (2H, d), 1.5 (3H, t), 1.1 (9H, s).

L-Prolinyl ethyl ester 11 : To a stirred, ice-cold suspension of proline (1.7 g, 0.015 mol) in absolute ethanol (50 ml), thionyl chloride (2.73 g, 1.7 ml, 1.5 eq) was added dropwise and the mixture was refluxed for 3–4 h. The reaction mixture was then allowed to stand overnight and the ethanol was evaporated *in vacuo* to leave proline ester hydrochloride as a viscous colourless liquid, which was stirred with dry diethyl ether. The ether was removed by evaporation leaving a viscous colourless liquid (2.49 g, 90%); ν_{\max} 1730 cm⁻¹ (CO); δ_H 4.3 (1H, m), 4.0 (2H, q, J 7 Hz), 2.6 (2H, m), 1.9 (4H, t), 1.4 (3H, t, J 7 Hz). The resulting L-prolinyl ethyl ester hydrochloride (3.4 g) was dissolved in water and washed with a saturated solution of potassium carbonate. The mixture was then extracted with diethyl ether (5 × 15 ml). The organic layers were combined and evaporated to give a yellow paste (0.25 g, 10%).

t-Butyloxycarbonyl-L-tryptophyl-L-proline ethyl ester 12 : To a solution of the Boc-protected tryptophan derivative **10** (0.9 g, 4.5 mmol) in dry DCM (20 ml) were added L-proline ethyl ester hydrochloride (0.73 g, 4.1 mmol) and DCC (0.85 g, 4.1 mmol), triethylamine (5 ml) and hydroxybenzotriazole (0.55 g, 1 eq) when a white solid precipitated out. The mixture was stirred for 24 h and the precipitate was filtered off. The filtrate was evaporated to give a yellow paste, which was purified by column chromatography (EtOAc/hex, 1 : 1) and the fractions with R_f = 0.85 were collected and evaporated to give a yellow paste (1.39 g, 74%); ν_{\max} 1710 (CO, ester), 1690 (CO, urethane) and 1660 cm⁻¹ (CO, amide); δ_H 8.2 (1H, s), 7.3 (5H, m), 4.4 (1H, m), 4.2 (1H, m), 4.0 (2H, m), 3.2 (2H, d), 2.6 (1H, m), 1.9 (4H, m), 1.5 (3H, t), 1.1 (9H, s).

L-Tryptophyl-L-proline ethyl ester 13 : To a stirred solution of the Boc-protected dipeptide **12** (1.40 g, 3.73 mmol) in DCM, trifluoroacetic acid was added. The mixture was stirred for 5 h while monitoring by TLC (hex : EtOAc, 2 : 1, R_f 0.67). The reaction mixture was washed with a saturated solution of potassium carbonate and extracted with Et₂O. The combined organic extracts was evaporated and a brownish paste was obtained (1.0 g, 85%); ν_{\max} 3500 (NH), 1715 (CO, ester), 1690 cm⁻¹ (CO, amide); δ_H 8.3 (2H, s), 7.5 (5H, m), 4.4 (1H, m), 4.2 (1H, m), 4.0 (2H, t), 3.2 (2H, d), 2.6 (2H, m), 1.5 (4H, m).

Cyclo(L-tryptophyl-L-proline) 6 : To a stirred solution of the deprotected dipeptide **13** (1.0 g, 3 mmol) in ethylene glycol (10 ml) potassium carbonate (~25 mg) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 36 h and monitored by TLC (EtOAc/MeOH, 1 : 1). On evaporation of the solvent a yellow paste was obtained. A minimum amount of water was added to it and the product was extracted in DCM. The organic extract was evaporated and a yellow paste was obtained (0.26 g, 30%); δ_H 7.5 (5H, m, ArH), 4.2 (2H, m), 3.7 (2H, m), 2.5 (1H, m), 1.7 (4H, m), m/z (CI) 312 (M + NH₄⁺), 284 (M + H⁺), 120 (base peak).

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